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Deciphering bioluminescent communication in marine annelids

Determining how bioluminescence mediates inter- and intraspecies communication at a behavioural and neuronal level

1. Excellence

1.1 State of the art, knowledge needs and project objectives

“Life Below Water” is not only one of the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals and in dire need of research for its appropriate protection, the oceans are also the origin of the most complex structure known to man: the brain¹. Marine animals can therefore provide insights into the evolution of functions vital to all complex nervous systems, of which interpreting and acting on sensory cues is the most important. In the deep, dark ocean a prominent cue is bioluminescence. The importance of this light to life below water is immense: an astonishing 76% of pelagic organisms have been reported to produce it^{2,3} and they often control emissions via their nervous system⁴. The assumed functions of bioluminescence are diverse, ranging from predator defence to hunting and mating⁴. The timing and colour of the produced light is thought to play a role in mediating these functions as durations vary and a range of hues are represented. These colours are, however, unevenly distributed among species. This, in turn, has led to the hypothesis that the rare yellow wavelength facilitates private, intraspecies communication while the more common blue and green, which have a longer range, also contribute to interspecies communication⁴. Whether or not this is the case remains unknown as **we still know very little about what bioluminescent signals mean and less about the significance of colour.**

This lack of knowledge about bioluminescent communication is due to the fact that the majority of our interpretations regarding its use are mostly limited to studies of animal morphology, not behaviour; *in situ* observations of individual bioluminescent signals are uncommon and experiments with live animals rare^{5,6}, because recording these often faint and short-lived signals is difficult. Recent technological developments involving remotely operated vehicles and highly sensitive cameras enable deep, underwater imaging and are improving opportunities for *in situ* observations, revealing the hidden diversity of bioluminescent species and signals, but still remain largely descriptive⁷. Behavioural experiments are rare partly due to the difficulty of obtaining and maintaining specimens in good condition as the taxa with the highest proportions of bioluminescent species consist of gelatinous zooplankton², which are often fragile⁸. **Laboratory studies are, however, the only way to decipher the true function of bioluminescence.** For example: dinoflagellates have long been known to bioluminesce in response to mechanical disturbance. However, controlled experiments were essential to show that the signal’s *function* is to deter predation^{9,10} by acting as a warning signal¹¹, which elicits high-speed swimming burst in grazing predators^{12–14} and attracts secondary predators¹¹. One other notable exception to the dearth of behavioural studies is the finding that an annelid from the Tomopteridae family, *Tomopteris helgolandica* (**Figure 1**), seems able to distinguish between the bioluminescent colour of its own species and that of others¹⁵. Specifically, artificial light signals mimicking conspecifics seem to attract these animals, while other signals repel¹⁵, perhaps because they could indicate the presence of predators. In addition, similarities in the anatomical structure and neural control of the light emitting organs of different *Tomopteris* species suggest that they may share a common origin¹⁶. Combined, these findings indicate a **potential for complex intra- and interspecies bioluminescent communication strategies and behaviours in related annelids.**

The bioluminescent emission of *Tomopteris* is under neural control; their light organs are innervated by nerve fibres^{17,18} and emission depends on the activation of nicotinic cholinergic receptors and calcium channels¹⁹. However, how their brain processes bioluminescent signals, including colour, is entirely unknown. Are the negative (predation) and positive (mating) outcomes that may be predicted by colour represented by different neuronal populations? **To fully understand the significance of bioluminescent signals to an organism, behavioural experiments need to be combined with readouts of neuronal activity.** This pioneering project will **determine how bioluminescence mediates inter- and intraspecies communication in marine annelids at a behavioural and neuronal level.** We will achieve this by using two *Tomopteris* species, both of which are common, locally accessible, and ideally suited for the following reasons: first, and most importantly, they possess unique bioluminescent profiles: *T. helgolandica* emits yellow light, while the related *T. planktonis* (**Figure 1**) uses the much

Figure 1: Two local *Tomopteris* species *T. helgolandica* and *T. planktonis* (insert, to scale) under white light.

more prevalent blue¹⁶, which allows for comparisons of two potentially different communication strategies. Second, they have evolved a convenient trait to conceal themselves from predators: they are transparent at all life stages. This means it is possible to identify neuronal populations both with traditional methods that require tissue sectioning and with new, complementary cutting-edge optical techniques that enable visualisation of introduced fluorescent markers in intact animals. Third, as pelagic predators they have a wide behavioural repertoire¹⁵ that, in combination with their relatively large size (up to 6 cm in length), enables detailed behavioural readouts. Fourth, unlike many other gelatinous marine organisms, they are known to remain healthy under laboratory conditions for weeks after collection in the wild, and in my lab we are able to keep them alive for months. This makes continuous behavioural observations and rigorous experimental protocols possible to implement. Fifth, because these species are thought to share a recent, common ancestor¹⁶, an evolutionary perspective on the use of bioluminescent colours and neuronal basis of its interpretation is attainable. This **unique combination of features** is, to the best of our knowledge, not easily attainable in any other annelid family. **Along with behavioural experiments and neurobiological techniques** they will allow us to fulfil two overarching objectives, pursued with a multidisciplinary approach:

Objective 1: Decipher the bioluminescent signals of two related annelid species

Objective 2: Identify neuronal populations activated by colour in these species

The group I have assembled to achieve these objectives has extensive experience with systems neuroscience, animal behaviour, marine biology, and the methods that will be employed in this ambitious project. We are thus in a unique position to bridge these fields with innovative experiments to shed light on a major, yet largely unexplored, ecological phenomenon. This enables us to pioneer a novel research line with the overarching vision of **revealing the evolutionary, behavioural, and neuronal origins of bioluminescent communication**. Understanding how “Life Below Water” communicates will be imperative to minimise our increasing impact on this ecosystem that is the cradle of both life and the nervous system.

1.2 Research questions and hypotheses, theoretical approach and methodology

The two overarching objectives will be addressed through four work packages (WPs):

WP1: Identify naturalistic stimuli associated with bioluminescent emission

WP2: Establish whether distinct properties of bioluminescent signals elicit different behaviours

WP3: Determine if *T. helgolandica* and *T. planktonis* can communicate with each other

WP4: Identify neuronal populations activated by different colours of bioluminescence

Together, these WPs will allow us to decipher the bioluminescent communication of two related species and identify the neuronal populations involved. This will be achieved by identifying naturalistic stimuli that evoke bioluminescent emission (WP1), whether distinct properties of bioluminescent signals elicit different behaviours (WP2), and if these two species react to the signals emitted by the other species. If so, we will determine if the meaning of the signal is conserved or if it is lost in a different colour (WP3). Finally, the neuronal populations activated by, and potentially interpreting, different bioluminescent colours will be identified (WP4). To succeed a wide range of methods, from specimen collection in the wild to behavioural and molecular analyses and histological techniques, will be used, as described below.

General methodology

For all WPs, *T. helgolandica* and *T. planktonis* specimens will be collected using large plankton nets in the Trondheim fjord at 300 m depth. As the project progresses, we will also test traps that use light to attract them, as a potentially efficient and gentler collection method²⁰. After collection and initial identification (in addition to bioluminescent colour, the two species can be distinguished by size, number of parapodia and presence of a tail¹⁶), they will be kept in aquariums in dedicated facilities at NTNU Trondhjem Biological Station (TBS). Here, fresh seawater is pumped up from 100 m depth in the Trondheim fjord to provide a constant supply of ambient seawater. The animals will be kept in the dark at 10°C, mimicking their natural habitat, and the water exchanged every few days. **We are able to keep them healthy, and bioluminescent, under these conditions for up to 5 months.** Holding conditions will be further optimised with expert advice from in-house technicians and our network, e.g. by setting up tanks with continuous water flow. All behavioural experiments (WPs 1-3) will be performed in the dark by video monitoring individual animals under infrared light. This method has already been successfully established in my lab (**Figure 2**). Bioluminescent emission will be monitored in parallel with a separate, high-sensitivity camera able to detect these faint signals in colour (**Figure 3**) and the two video feeds synchronised with Bonsai²¹. To track the

Figure 2: Tomopteris in IR light
Single frame from video of a *T. helgolandica* moving in darkness illuminated with infrared light.

behaviour of one or more individuals, recently developed deep-learning algorithms at the forefront of the field, such as DeepLabCut²² and SLEAP²³, will be employed, enabling marker-less tracking. 3D tracking will be developed in collaboration with Assoc. Prof. Dunn (see section 3.1) to enable more detailed quantification of behaviour in more naturalistic environments. In addition, despite the Tomopteridae being a common annelid family that is found globally, their species diversity is poorly understood as their fragility has often meant damage to key morphological traits during processing. To ensure correct species identification, the identity of all animals will be confirmed with DNA barcoding after experiments (using the tail region, keeping the head region for histology) in collaboration with project partner Dr. Majaneva (see section 3.1), who is an expert in integrated taxonomy of zooplankton, including *Tomopteris*. Additional WP-specific methods are described in their respective sections below.

WP1: Identify naturalistic stimuli associated with bioluminescent emission

Rationale and hypotheses: while bioluminescence can be triggered by strong mechanical, chemical, or electrical stimulation in *Tomopteris*^{15,16}, spontaneous bioluminescence is rarely observed in single-housed *T. helgolandica* specimens¹⁵. This suggests that naturally occurring emission is likely associated with physiologically relevant stimuli, such as the presence of predators, prey, or conspecifics. The rare, yellow colour used by *T. helgolandica* (**Figure 3**)

Figure 3: Bioluminescence
T. helgolandica (left), *T. planktonis* (right). Acquired with collab. Garm

further suggests it might be using bioluminescence primarily for intraspecies communication. **We therefore hypothesise that *T. helgolandica* is more likely to emit these signals when with conspecifics compared to when they are alone.** Further, **we hypothesise that *T. planktonis*' more common blue bioluminescence is more likely to be elicited during (interspecies) prey/predator interactions than *T. helgolandica*'s yellow.**

Methodology: to determine which stimuli are associated with bioluminescent emission, three sets of experiments will be performed on both *T. helgolandica* and *T. planktonis* while monitoring both behaviour and bioluminescence. **First, single animals will be exposed to stimuli simulating potential predators** (real predators are avoided so animals can be reused). Replicating a previous study on *T. helgolandica*¹⁵ and extending it to *T. planktonis*, plastic pipettes will be used to simulate potential predators by creating water disturbances at various locations and distances from each individual. Expanding on this established method, surface transducers will be used to create more quantifiable vibrations in their environment on different substrates, including the aquarium wall and through dummy predators (submerged fish models). **Second, the same individuals will be exposed to live prey.** The literature is conflicted regarding what *Tomopteris* feed on²⁴, but larger individuals are known to eat smaller *Tomopteris* specimens and oocytes if offered²⁵. They are also thought to eat other zooplankton. Different zooplankton found in the same net samples (an indication that they occupy the same habitat as our species) will therefore be used, as well as readily available copepods at several, defined, developmental stages (*Calanus finmarchicus* cultures, NTNU SeaLab and European Research Network for Marine Biology). Prey will be introduced in increasing numbers to see if abundance affects bioluminescent emission and when their size deems it possible their position relative to *Tomopteris* will be tracked. **Third, single animals will be exposed to members of their own species.** One common purpose for intraspecies communication is the identification of suitable mates, in which case maturation stage and availability of potential partners are likely to matter. Individuals will therefore be introduced to 1) conspecifics of various maturation stages and 2) increasing numbers of maturation-matched conspecifics. Maturation stage will be determined by the number of parapodia, as this number increases with age²⁵. If predation on conspecifics is observed, then a transparent barrier/net will be placed between the individuals. In all three sets of experiments the different stimulus types will be presented on different days to avoid interaction effects. Each stimulus type will be repeated 10 times per animal, and each repeat preceded by a 2-minute baseline period serving as an internal no-stimulus control. The time between repetitions will be adjusted according to the time it takes for bioluminescent emission and/or stimulus-induced movement to return to baseline. All instances of bioluminescence (both stimulus-associated and spontaneous) will be analysed for their timing relative to the start of the stimulus presentation, their duration, and maximum intensity, and compared across stimulus- and baseline periods.

Expected outcomes and impact: experiments in WP1 will yield a comprehensive overview of bioluminescent and movement responses to a large variety of physiologically relevant stimuli for two *Tomopteris* species. By comparing responses across species, we will be able to collect the first evidence for whether the evolutionary change in colour has influenced the conditions under which bioluminescence is used. As one of the first experiments of its kind, it will pave the way for similar studies in other bioluminescent species.

Risks and their management: low to moderate risk. A working setup for monitoring *Tomopteris* behaviour is already established in my lab (**Figure 2**) and we can capture their bioluminescence on video (**Figure 3**). We will receive expert advice from collaborators Prof. Mallefet and Assoc. Prof. Garm (see section 3.1), both of whom have extensive experience imaging bioluminescent species, including *Tomopteris*, to ensure consistent progress. Imaging and analysis in 3D carry more risk, but hiring a Postdoctoral Fellow with a relevant technical background, and support from Assoc. Prof. Dunn who has ample experience with both, reduce it.

WP2: Establish whether distinct properties of bioluminescent signals elicit different behaviours

Rationale and hypothesis: the properties of bioluminescent signals, such as their duration, pattern, and brightness, can contain information⁵. Ostracod crustaceans, for example, use bright, long, high-frequency signals and dim, short, uniform pulses, all blue, to differentiate between two phases of their courtship display²⁶. Further, the number of bioluminescent flashes emitted by artificial dinoflagellate predators modulates ostracod swimming behaviour¹⁴. The yellow-emitter *T. helgolandica* is also capable of producing different bioluminescent patterns, a “glow” and “flash” response that depend on the concentration of a chemical stimulus¹⁹, and they respond differently to these patterns if presented in blue but not if presented in yellow¹⁵. Our preliminary data further show that swimming behaviour only changes if a blue signal is >1 second long (**Figure 4**), indicating that the duration of interspecies bioluminescent signals is meaningful. However, the significance of the distinct intraspecies signals remains a mystery. A reason for this may be that the “glow” and “flash” signals are less informative individually than when presented in sequences incorporating both, as observed *in situ*²⁷. Hence, **we hypothesise that real versus scrambled bioluminescent signals will elicit distinct behavioural responses in both *T. helgolandica* and the related *T. planktonis*.**

Figure 4: Effect of signal duration
Blue light stimuli longer than one second result in a *T. helgolandica* swimming faster. 0=no change in swim speed, 1=faster swim speed.

Methodology: to determine if distinct signal properties elicit different behaviours, we will use miniature light emitting diodes (LEDs) with emission spectra resembling those of the blue and yellow-emitting *Tomopteris* to simulate the bioluminescence of each species. Preliminary data from my lab show that they respond to such LED light (**Figures 4-5**), in line with previous results^{13,15}. The LEDs will be arranged in spatial patterns mimicking the light organ distribution of real *Tomopteris*. Individual animals will be presented with two types of light patterns that **1) mimic the naturally^{15,19,27,28} occurring bioluminescent signals of their species** (as observed in WP1) and **2) are scrambled versions of those patterns** (different inter-flash intervals, pulse durations, intensities, and patterns, varied systematically). The different stimulus types will be presented 10 times each in randomised interleaved trials across several days, each preceded by a 2-minute baseline period serving both as an internal no-stimulus control and to avoid potential habituation/sensitisation effects. Changes in acceleration, body undulation, movement direction, velocity and tortuosity²⁹ in response to each stimulus as compared to baseline will be monitored.

Expected outcomes and impact: experiments from WP2 will result in detailed readouts of behavioural responses to distinct signal properties in two *Tomopteris* species. In addition, we expect to determine if *Tomopteris* bioluminesce in response to light signals, of which there is currently conflicting and limited evidence^{15,28}. This WP will hence elucidate which properties of bioluminescent signals are behaviourally relevant, aiding our interpretation of the function of similar signals in other species considerably.

Risks and their management: low to moderate risk. As we already have a working setup, preliminary data, and a collaborator who has performed similar experiments before, most risks associated with this WP are minimal. However, though responses to artificial light signals have been observed both by us (**Figures 4-5**) and others^{13,15}, responses to specific signal properties may be subtle and hence challenging to distinguish¹⁵. To ensure that behavioural effects are not lost to ‘noise’, cutting-edge software^{22,23} that enables detailed tracking will be employed, including the orientation of specimens relative to the light stimulus, as they may be insensitive to stimuli from certain egocentric directions. Similarly, close attention will be paid to any habituation/sensitisation effects that may influence the results and the trial intervals changed accordingly.

WP3: Determine if *T. helgolandica* and *T. planktonis* can communicate with each other

Rationale and hypothesis: because blue and green wavelengths dominate in the ocean, the visual system of most species is also typically centred around these wavelengths⁴. The yellow-emitting *T. helgolandica* seems to be an exception, however, as it appears able to discriminate between blue and yellow signals¹⁵. Although that study did not compare light intensities (see ‘methodology’), the findings suggest a capacity for interspecies (in addition to intraspecies) communication, including sensitivity to the blue signals emitted by

T. planktonis. **For the first time, our preliminary data further shows that red light elicits behavioural responses (Figure 5)**, indicating that *T. helgolandica* is sensitive to several wavelengths. Whether the same is true for *T. planktonis* is unknown, but one study suggests that yellow bioluminescence might have evolved from blue¹⁶. If so, the blue-emitter *T. planktonis* may be unable to discriminate between blue and yellow because it represents an evolutionary stage in which yellow sensitivity has not yet developed. Hence, **we hypothesise that signals emitted by *T. planktonis* result in behavioural and/or bioluminescent responses from *T. helgolandica*, but not vice versa.**

Methodology: to determine if these two species respond differently to intra- vs. interspecies signals, we will run two sets of experiments. **First, individuals will be exposed to artificial bioluminescent signals that only vary in colour.** These experiments will be performed as in WP2, except the temporal signatures of each species' naturally occurring bioluminescence will also be presented in the colour used by the other species. Three light intensities covering two log units will be used, as the ability to discriminate colours may not be due to colour vision *per se*, but a detection of intensity enabled by their opsin's spectral sensitivity (see WP4 'risks').

Second, individuals will be introduced to members of the other species. These experiments will be a continuation of the third set described in WP1 (where single animals are introduced to conspecifics), enabling a comparison of behaviours and interactions between individuals of the same (WP1) versus another *Tomopteris* species (this WP). These experiments will therefore be performed in the same manner, including individuals of all maturation stages as it remains unknown how the developmental trajectories between the two species compare. To eliminate potential confounding variables (e.g. touch or predation) a subset of these experiments will be performed with a transparent barrier between individuals. **Expected outcomes and impact:** results from WP3 will provide a comprehensive overview of behavioural responses to both artificial and actual members of another, related species for two *Tomopteris* annelids. These findings will determine if the two species can communicate with each other despite their differing bioluminescent colours and **provide important evidence for, or against, the hypothesis that yellow light signals mainly facilitate intraspecies interactions while blue light is used for both intra- and interspecies communication.** The use of two related species also means that these findings will have a significant impact on theories concerning the evolutionary origin of bioluminescent colours.

Risks and their management: low to moderate risk. This WP has the same risks as WPs 1-2 as the experiments are similar. Given the measures described there we are confident we can also carry out WP3 successfully.

WP4: Identify neuronal populations activated by different colours of bioluminescence

Rationale and hypotheses: if *T. helgolandica* uses colour to distinguish between other species (potential predators, negative predictive value) and conspecifics (potential mates, positive predictive value), then different colours should result in the activation of different neuronal populations to ensure appropriate behaviour³⁰. In contrast, *T. planktonis* may not respond to yellow at all (WP3). Whether this is due to an inability to detect the stimulus or a lack of relevance, however, can only be determined by observing neuronal activity. A well-established method for identifying activated neurons, including photoreceptors and other retinal cells³¹, is immunohistological detection of the nuclear protein product of immediate early gene (IEG) *c-fos*: c-Fos³². The activation of IEGs has primarily been studied in mammals, but is also detected in marine invertebrates such as molluscs³³ and cnidarians³⁴. Further, **our preliminary data shows, for the first time, c-Fos expression in *Tomopteris* (Figure 6B)**, demonstrating its promise as a tool to identify activated neurons in annelids. **We hypothesise that 1) the pattern of c-Fos expression in the eyes and brain of *T. helgolandica* will be different after exposure to yellow and blue light signals, and 2) that comparing the pattern observed in *T. planktonis* during baseline and after exposure to yellow light will determine whether or not yellow signals are detected and considered salient.**

Methodology: to establish whether different colours activate different neuronal populations, **we first need to determine if c-Fos expression is indeed a result of neuronal activity in *Tomopteris*.** To do so, we will anaesthetise animals with menthol (found to be effective in *Tomopteris*¹⁹), dissect parapodial segments and expose these to either the depolarising agent KCl (which induces bioluminescence through neural pathways¹⁹) or seawater as an internal control. A subset of experiments will be performed on whole animals

Figure 5: Responses to colours

Maximum intensity projections across 3 seconds immediately before (left) and after (right) a white (top) or red (bottom) light stimulus, showing forward movement and curling, respectively, in *T. helgolandica*.

to ensure the dissection itself does not occlude the results. Using bioluminescence as a readout of successful activation, we will then fix and stain the samples with immunofluorescent methods, including DAPI to label cell nuclei and acetyl-alpha tubulin to label neuronal structures (both established in *Tomopteris*^{35–37}) in addition to c-Fos (Figure 6). Different temporal delays before fixation will be tested to determine the time course of c-Fos expression in *Tomopteris*. If nuclear c-Fos expression is higher after KCl exposure compared to control, and it co-localises with acetyl-alpha tubulin, this is a strong indication that c-Fos expression reflects neuronal activation. We will then combine traditional and cutting-edge techniques to address our hypotheses. **First, we will employ methods with which I am an expert** and that I and others^{35–37} have found to work well in *Tomopteris*. Here, individual specimens of both species will be preserved using a formalin-based protocol following exposure to artificial bioluminescent signals that are either yellow or blue and of different intensities (as in WP3, to see if light intensity affects activation patterns) or no light as a baseline control. To control for potential movement responses, stimuli that evoke movements similar to those evoked by light (data from WP1), but do not involve light, will be used (see ‘risks’). Then, thin (10–40 μm), horizontal (for optimal view of the brain) or sagittal (to best identify retinal cells³⁸) serial sections of their heads will be made. These sections will be stained as described above. Confocal microscopy will be used to confirm overlap between markers and the images analysed blind to the experimental condition to identify numbers and anatomical locations of cells that are c-Fos positive. **Second, we will use cutting-edge methods that enable 3D maps of these populations to be generated from intact animals.** By using a newly described protocol that shows improved preservation of gelatinous organisms³⁹, the reduction in transparency associated with traditional fixation methods can be avoided. This protocol is also compatible with immunohistochemistry³⁹, which in combination with the exceptional transparency of *Tomopteris* makes examinations with light-sheet microscopy ideal. Using the same molecular markers, this approach will complement the traditional method, avoiding tissue distortions that can occur with sectioning and **provide a detailed spatial map of activated neuronal populations in annelids for the first time.**

Expected outcomes and impact: WP4 will **provide evidence at a neural level for, or against, the hypothesis that the colour of bioluminescent signals carries meaning.** The obtained results will also determine whether this is true for two related species, providing important insights into the evolution of colour as a cue. Further, they will **pioneer a new research line into the neuronal underpinnings of bioluminescence**, providing an essential foundation for studies aiming to uncover the physiological basis of bioluminescent communication. **Risks and their management:** **high risk.** This WP relies on the validation of c-Fos as a marker of activity. While well-established in mammals and expressed in *Tomopteris* (Figure 6), it may not correlate with neuronal activity in the latter. If it does not, we will test other IEGs found in invertebrates, such as *c-jun* and *Egr*⁴⁰ (performing *in situ* hybridisation if immunostaining proves inconclusive). If it does, then the neuronal populations activated by each colour may still be difficult to distinguish (e.g. if they are anatomically intermingled). If so, we will use additional markers established in *Tomopteris* that may help tease them apart, such as serotonin³⁵. If populations overlap both in the eye and in the brain, this may indicate that colours are not interpreted using separate pathways, but by using coding schemes, such as rate coding (e.g. only one opsin is expressed but its spectral sensitivity means different wavelengths elicit different firing rates at the same light intensity). Movements may also confound our analysis: c-Fos expression resulting from movement may occlude expression related to visual processing. Should our movement control not be sufficient, then we will repeat the experiments in anaesthetised intact animals or dissected prostomia, and as a last resort in pharmacologically paralysed animals if it turns out that anaesthesia subdues evoked c-Fos expression. The remaining risks are low considering our preliminary data, my extensive experience with the traditional approach and previous studies on the neuroanatomy of *Tomopteris*^{35–38}. The protocols may need to be adapted to work with the new fixation method, but with the availability of detailed protocols for intact animals^{35,39} we are confident these obstacles will be overcome. Light-sheet microscopy carries minimal risks as it is a widely used technique, a commercial system is in current use at the Kavli Institute for Systems Neuroscience (KISN), and I have over a decade worth of experience with a wide variety of microscopes. Further, the most troublesome step in preparing samples for light-sheet imaging, tissue clearing, is of no consequence since our samples are transparent. Should light-sheet imaging still prove problematic, then the

Figure 6: c-Fos in *T. helgolandica*

A) Epifluorescence image of DAPI-labelled cells in the brain. **B)** Single z-plane 40x confocal images showing expression of c-Fos in one of two DAPI stained cells.

transparency and small size of our samples means confocal and 2-photon microscopy are valid alternatives. State-of-the-art microscopes of both kinds are readily available at KISN, and I am an expert user of both.

Summary: Results from WPs 1-3 will address Objective 1 by providing some of the first experimental insights into how bioluminescence is used, how members of the same and related species respond to it, and the significance of colour. WP4 addresses Objective 2 by identifying, for the first time, neuronal populations activated by bioluminescent colours. The findings will have extensive implications for our understanding of these light signals and set an important and timely precedent for experiments in other species. This will be crucial to determine if our findings generalise and to increase the much-needed research effort into an ecosystem on which we are having a substantial impact.

General risks and their management

In addition to WP-specific risks (detailed above), general risks are also considered: First, we need to collect specimens. While there are variations in the abundance of *T. helgolandica* in the Trondheim fjord through the year, they are never absent⁴¹. We also typically find both species in the same net samples and in good condition throughout the year, and with an immediate vicinity to collection sites (each field trip totals 5-6 hrs), and collaborations with other groups collecting plankton samples in the area, the risk of not gathering enough animals is minimised. Second, behavioural experiments with wild, aquarium-housed animals means long-term maintenance is important. We can keep specimens in good condition for up to 5 months in my lab, enabling longitudinal observations of individual animals. Third, we aim to track individuals in 3D, which allows for more detailed readouts of behaviour, especially in the z-dimension, but is also a technically demanding task. With expert support from collaborator Assoc. Prof. Dunn, and recruitment of a Postdoctoral Fellow with a technical background, the risk of not achieving this within a reasonable timeframe is reduced, but should it prove too time consuming then the current, functional 2D setup is still sufficient for collecting all data needed. Fourth, the fragile nature of *Tomopteris* means the known species diversity is limited⁴². Thus, morphological identification may not be sufficient to determine which species we work with. Project partner Dr. Majaneva will therefore perform molecular identification of all specimens used in our experiments, using an established protocol developed in-house, to ensure the results we obtain are attributed to the correct species. Fifth, with minimised methodological risks the main risks become conceptual: the behavioural responses observed in the lab may not be identical to those in the wild, leading to inconclusive results. We will reduce this risk by replicating the conditions observed in the wild as closely as possible, including fresh seawater collected from similar depths at which these annelids are found (part of TBS infrastructure) and using spacious aquariums with moderate currents to support their pelagic nature. Similarly, although *T. helgolandica* does not appear to display seasonal variations in maturation²⁵, the differences in relative abundance throughout the year might result in an alteration of bioluminescent signals, especially if they are used for intraspecies communication. We have therefore allocated time to perform WP1 experiments four times throughout one year to capture any potential seasonal variations. If such effects are found, then the timing of remaining WPs will be adjusted accordingly, and these novel findings explored in separate project applications. Finally, although related, the individual WPs can be performed independently and do not fully depend on each other for success, further minimising the overall risk of the project. Any additional, emerging risks and mitigation strategies will be communicated and addressed in team meetings as soon as they arise.

Ethics

As this proposal aims to decipher bioluminescent communication, the use of animals is necessary. However, the annelids in this proposal are zooplankton, whose use in research is not regulated, and all experiments involve procedures that are either non-invasive, terminal, or when possible performed under anaesthesia. Ethical concerns regarding animal experiments are therefore minimal. Nonetheless, we will still comply with the “Three Rs” of humane experimental technique by using a simple model (replacement), the lowest number of animals possible by using individuals in several experiments (reduction), and optimise housing and handling conditions to minimise distress and enhance animal welfare (refinement).

1.3 Novelty and ambition

Our skilled, cross-disciplinary team will enable the ambitious behavioural experiments of WPs 1-3 to be among the first in the field to help us decipher what bioluminescent signals mean and their importance for the organisms themselves. With techniques never before used in marine annelids, WP4 will for the first time map neuronal populations activated by bioluminescent signals. We will thus **gain direct and unprecedented insights into how bioluminescence is used that go beyond morphological and physiological inferences**. As such, this unique interdisciplinary project will pioneer the use of state-of-the-art systems neuroscience

methods to **reveal the evolutionary, behavioural, and neuronal origins of bioluminescent communication**. It will thus spearhead novel research lines into the fundamental principles of marine nervous systems.

2. Impact

2.1 Potential for academic impact of the research project

While previous morphological and physiological studies of bioluminescence are valuable, they remain largely descriptive and cannot tell us how or why these light signals are used. This pioneering project will determine how bioluminescence, and crucially the colour of bioluminescence, mediates inter- and intraspecies communication. **The results will have an immediate and significant impact on our understanding of the function and relevance of the predominant source of light in the deep**, and with two related species provide an additional evolutionary perspective. Consequently, it will stimulate additional research and **inform research performed in the field, where the use of light may have dramatic consequences**⁴³. By mapping the neuronal populations activated by bioluminescent signals, the project will contribute insights into how bioluminescent signals are processed and **spearhead investigations into the hitherto unexplored neuronal basis of bioluminescent communication**. This will lay the essential foundation for future neurophysiological work, including an **application to the European Research Council with a goal to establish, for the first time, *in vivo* imaging of neural function in non-transgenic gelatinous animals**. The accessibility and transparency of *Tomopteris* make them ideal for non-invasive optical approaches with high cell-yield, **enabling the functional connectivity of circuits processing bioluminescent signals to be determined**. Using state-of-the-art techniques, the interdisciplinary approach of this project will advance both the fields of marine biology and neuroscience, contribute to the UN's Sustainable Development Goal 14.A, and have extensive implications for our understanding of neural function in all species, whose nervous systems evolved from the same habitat in which these marine annelids still live.

Measures for monitoring successful project impact include completion of 1) each WP, 2) the activities described in section 2.3 below, and 3) the additional milestones and deliverables listed in **Figure 7**. To ensure reproducibility and reuse, results will be published in conjunction with datasets, metadata and analysis code, all made openly available and complying with the FAIR principles, as described in section 2.3 below.

2.3 Measures for communication and exploitation

Project results will be presented and discussed in several ways for a wide range of audiences. This will include internal, departmental seminars at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences (MH) and the Faculty of Natural Sciences (NV, NTNU) and both general and more field specific national and international conferences. Specifically, we aim to present at conferences such as the International Symposium on Bioluminescence and Chemiluminescence (ISBC), the International Congress on Neuroethology (ICN), the Society for Neuroscience (SfN) meeting, the Deep Sea Biology Society (DSBS) meeting, the Platynereis meeting (PM), and the Nordic Neuroscience (NNS) meeting (see **Figure 7** for anticipated calendar, subject to change with release of dates). Other conferences that we will consider on a case-by-case basis include the Federation of European Neuroscience Societies Forum (FENS), the European Marine Biology Symposium, and the Association for the Study of Animal Behaviour meetings. The protocols and results of DNA barcoding will also be discussed at the annual meeting of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) and in their working groups on Integrated Morphological and Molecular Taxonomy (WGIMT) and Zooplankton Ecology (WGZE), where Dr. Majaneva is a member. We will make a data management plan at the beginning of the project period that complies with the FAIR principles for scientific data management: data, metadata, code, and analyses will be stored securely using dedicated NTNU infrastructure and made available in open repositories such as EBRAINS and my lab's existing GitHub repository. Open-source research software (e.g. Python) will be used to promote reuse. Results will be shared in preprints on bioRxiv for immediate availability to the community and then published in open access, peer reviewed articles. **We aim to publish 4 primary research manuscripts, all in non-profit journals such as eLife, Biology Open and PLOS journals to ensure the science is widely accessible and as a result has the largest possible impact**. We also plan to publish a review summarising the current state and outlook within the field of bioluminescent communication at the end of the project period. Press releases and the KISN annual report will further serve to highlight work and specific findings from the project, and to communicate them to the general public. We will also communicate and disseminate our work in an accessible manner to non-academic audiences through online platforms and physical events – efforts that have already resulted in the award of a major science communication prize for an essay I wrote about bioluminescence research for a general audience. Major outreach efforts will take

place towards the end of each project year (**Figure 7**). This may include writing articles for *Frontiers for Young Minds*, *Gemini* and *forskersonen.no*, presenting during *Forskningsdagene* and *The European Researchers' Night*, and arranging workshops and lab tours associated with *Brain Awareness Week* and the *UN Decade of Ocean Science* initiatives. Finally, my lab website and dedicated Instagram and X accounts are regularly updated and will continue to be used to announce and describe project activities to all audiences throughout the project period. All activities will be aided by the dedicated communication teams at both KISN and NTNU.

3. Implementation

3.1 Project manager and project group

Project manager

Inspired by notable neuroscientists such as Eric Kandel, Alan Hodgkin and Andrew Huxley, I firmly believe that marine life holds the key to many unanswered questions about the brain. I therefore aim to **take my principal field, neuroscience, into the future by going back to where it all began: the ocean**. I am in a unique position to achieve this due to my training in several international world-leading research institutes with top scientists within the field of neuroscience, including Prof. Tara Keck at the Max Planck Institute of Neurobiology (Germany) and King's College London (UK, now at University College London), and Profs. May-Britt and Edvard Moser at NTNU (Norway). I have gained extensive experience with several cutting-edge techniques, including those employed in this project (behaviour, histology, imaging). By focusing on quality over quantity and pursuing ambitious projects, my work has generated considerable interest and is highly cited (see CV). Since the start of my own lab, the Marine Neuroscience Laboratory (MNL), I have developed **national and international collaborations, secured three grants, received funding for a PhD student to work full-time in my lab, won a major science communication award for my writing on bioluminescence, and received several invitations to speak about my work globally**. I have also been honoured with **membership in the Young Academy of Norway** and constantly develop my supervision abilities through courses and experience. I currently manage research projects at both KISN and MNL, including supervision of a PhD student in the latter, with simultaneous teaching commitments and sole responsibility for a course with 130 students at the Department of Biology (IBI, NTNU). My affiliation with both KISN and IBI, representing two different faculties, provides valuable insights and connections for my interdisciplinary MNL work.

Funding from the Researcher Project for Experienced Scientists will cement my independence and allow me to continue to bridge and lead both marine biology and neuroscience into novel, fruitful directions. It will also enable me to train a Postdoctoral Fellow, empowering my team and I to answer pressing questions in the field. I will dedicate 50% of my time to the project (the other 50% being teaching commitments).

Project group

The project team will consist of a PhD student (already working my lab, funded by NTNU), a Postdoctoral Fellow (to be hired, funded by this project), and a project partner (current collaborator, project related work funded by this project). In addition, three collaborators will provide expert advice at key stages of the project (see **Figure 7** for timeline and attached CVs for experience). The **PhD student**, Nadia van Eekelen, is trained in both neuroscience and marine biology and has previously worked with several marine species. She has already received training in behavioural and histology experiments with *Tomopteris* in the MNL and will dedicate 100% of her time to this project for the first 1.5 years. A **Postdoctoral Fellow** with a technical background (to complement the PhD's and my background) and experience with imaging and animal tracking will be recruited to work full-time on the project for the middle 3 years. I will tailor my support of both the PhD and Postdoctoral Fellow to ensure they receive the training and experience necessary to perform the project tasks at hand and prepare them for the career step they would like to pursue next. The **project partner**, Dr. Sanna Majaneva (Akvaplan-niva), is a marine ecologist specialised in zooplankton diversity and ecology. She has extensive experience collecting and identifying hard-to-identify fragile zooplankton and has for the last three years specifically worked with bioluminescent organisms (RCN project 315728). She will contribute to the project regularly throughout the project period by co-supervising the PhD student and be responsible for species identification and increasing the ecological context of the project. **Collaborator 1** Prof. Jérôme Mallefet (Université catholique de Louvain) has extensive experience with bioluminescent organisms, including performing behavioural experiments with *Tomopteris*. He will provide insights when optimising the setups for behaviour and designing light stimuli for WPs 1-3. **Collaborator 2** Assoc. Prof. Anders Garm (University of Copenhagen) is also an expert on bioluminescence, with experience eliciting and capturing bioluminescent emissions in colour in several species. He will provide advice on both aspects for WPs 1-3.

Collaborator 3 Assoc. Prof. Benjamin Dunn (Department of Mathematical Sciences, NTNU) is an expert in (neural) data analysis and has considerable experience building setups for 3D monitoring of naturalistic behaviour. He will help the Postdoctoral Fellow extend the current 2D setup for WPs 1-3.

Network: We will use our continuously expanding network of collaborators and supporters for guidance and assistance. This includes additional experts on bioluminescence, maintenance and culturing of marine invertebrates, and analysis methods, among others. We also seek and provide support in global communities, including the Arctic Marine Ecosystem Research Network, WGIMT and WGZE groups, plus the NeuroMethods (>15k members), FuturePI (>7.5k members), and Deep-Sea Biology Society (>900 members) Slack groups.

3.2 Project organisation and management

Work plan and strategy

The project will last four years and consists of four complementary WPs (**Figure 7**). Communication and dissemination measures outside the writing and publication of research manuscripts will take place throughout, with major outreach activities planned for the end of each year (e.g., producing larger articles/videos/presentations and participating in events, see section 2.3 and **Figure 7**). In the first six months, the PhD student (van Eekelen, currently in the lab and trained in the behavioural experiments) and I will collect data for WP1 using the 2D setup already in my lab, acquire the necessary equipment for building a 3D setup plus histology reagents, and advertise the postdoctoral position. The Postdoctoral Fellow will have experience with tracking and analysis of animal behaviour, and be responsible for the building, data acquisition and analysis relating to the 3D setup for WPs 1-3. When 2D data collection for WP1 is nearing completion (six months in) and in parallel to its data analysis (performed by the PhD), I will optimise protocols for WP4 with the PhD student (already trained in histological procedures), and train the Postdoctoral Fellow, when behavioural experiments are less time consuming (i.e., in between field trips). The PhD will focus on traditional histology methods and the Postdoctoral Fellow will additionally be involved in developing protocols for light-sheet imaging. I will contribute to both. The building and optimisation of setups for WPs 2-3 is expected to be faster as they share commonalities with WP1 and experimental protocols and analysis pipelines will be established by then. WPs 2-3 will be completed by the Postdoctoral Fellow and myself. Project partner Dr. Majaneva will contribute to sample collection, perform molecular species identification for all WPs, and provide a broader ecological perspective. Collaborators will contribute as described in sections 1 and 3.1, at the times indicated in **Figure 7**. The PhD and Postdoctoral Fellow will visit all collaborators to learn additional techniques and build their networks. Before completion of the PhD and towards the end of the project period all participants will gather to evaluate progress and prepare for project completion, respectively. Although each team member will contribute to some tasks more than others, all core team members will work closely together, discuss progress in weekly lab meetings, and be involved in both behavioural and histology experiments.

Research infrastructure and management structure

The multidisciplinary nature of this project means that it will take place in three locations (up to 5 km apart) ideally suited for the planned work. Behavioural experiments (WPs 1-3) will be performed at TBS in the NV Faculty (NTNU): TBS has facilities and technical expertise specifically tailored for marine biological research, with groups specialising in plankton and bioluminescence. Facilities include an adjacent pier for field trips on

Figure 7: Gantt chart with additional milestones and deliverables. See section 2.3 for descriptions of outreach and conference activities. X: timing of *major* outreach activity. Shapes: WP-specific (WP colour) contributions.

research vessels, a continuous seawater supply pumped up from the fjord (at 100 m depth) in which our species live, and climate-controlled rooms for housing organisms and conducting experiments. High performance computing needs will be fulfilled with the Idun cluster available at NTNU. Histology (WP4) will be performed at KISN in the MH Faculty (NTNU): KISN houses world-class core facilities and expertise for advanced processing and imaging of neural tissue. In addition to modern equipment for performing immunohistochemistry, a large suite of sophisticated microscopes (including a new light-sheet microscope) with dedicated support is available through NORBRAIN. Molecular species identification will be performed at the University Museum (UM) at the NV Faculty (NTNU): UM is part of the regional node of the International Barcode of Life project, housing state-of-the-art molecular labs and technical expertise tailored for the identification of a wide variety of species. An affiliation with all locations has already been well established through my work at KISN, my lab at TBS, and Dr. Majanevas work at UM.

The team will be managed by me, the project manager. I will directly supervise the PhD student and Postdoctoral Fellow and liaise closely with project partner Dr. Majaneva who also acts as co-supervisor for the PhD. This core team will be supported by collaborators Prof. Mallefet, Assoc. Profs. Garm and Dunn, in addition to the technical and administrative units available at TBS, KISN, and UM.

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Summary of marks

Criterion	Mark
Excellence – potential for advancing the state-of-the-art	6
Excellence – quality of R&D activities	5
Impact	5
Implementation	5

Criteria

Excellence – potential for advancing the state-of-the-art

The extent to which the proposed work is ambitious, novel, and goes beyond the state-of-the-art

- Scientific creativity and originality.
- Novelty and boldness of hypotheses or research questions.
- Potential for development of new knowledge beyond the current state-of-the-art, including significant theoretical, methodological, experimental or empirical advancement.

Strengths

- + The project is creative and original as it attempts to identify and understand bioluminescent signals in deep-dwelling organisms. The work can contribute new knowledge to neuroscience as well as deep-sea ecology and communication. This is a novel research line.
- + There is strong potential to develop new knowledge beyond the state-of-the-art covering both theoretical and empirical advancement. Improving the understanding of both intra- and inter-specific communication through bioluminescence will not only enhance basic understanding of communication in the deep sea but provides a basis for concluding whether increased human activity in the deep sea may interfere with such communication.

Shortcomings

- Although the proposal briefly mentions broader implications in terms of a wider understanding of the 'meaning' of bioluminescence, the proposal would have benefitted from greater consideration of how widely applicable the outcomes might be, given that "76% of pelagic organisms have been reported to produce it [bioluminescence]". It was unclear how well the annelid model would apply to other species or taxa.

Selected mark : 6 - Excellent

The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Only minor shortcomings are present.

Excellence – quality of R&D activities

The quality of the proposed R&D activities

- Quality of the research questions, hypotheses and project objectives, and the extent to which they are clearly and adequately specified.
- Credibility and appropriateness of the theoretical approach, research design and use of scientific methods.

Appropriate consideration of interdisciplinary approaches.

- The extent to which appropriate consideration has been given to ethical issues, safety issues, gender dimension in research content, and use of stakeholder/user knowledge if appropriate.

Strengths

- + The quality of the research questions and objectives are good, they are clearly stated and well-articulated.
- + The research attempts to reveal the (intra- and inter-specific) behavioural responses as well as the neuronal activation associated with bioluminescence. The work uses state-of-the-art techniques. The hypotheses are logical, well described and linked with specific experiments and measurements.
- + Some significant challenges have been highlighted in the proposal but risks are considered as are mitigation measures in each work package. This is very good and provides a level of confidence that the challenges of the experimental work are well understood.
- + Ethical issues have been considered in relation to animal manipulation even though the study organisms are not currently covered by legislation, which is a strength.

Shortcomings

- The research questions are somewhat simplistic in several WPs and do not fully address in the experimental design the complexity of the animals, their behavioural repertoire and non-bioluminescent stimuli, which is a shortcoming and reduces project credibility. For example, in WP1 (naturalistic stimuli) it is a concern that the basic biology and ecology of the annelids is not well established, and this may lead to confounding readouts. Furthermore, the complexity of biotic and abiotic stimuli the annelids are likely to experience in their environment do not appear to be contemplated in the trials and this is a shortcoming.
- This proposal requires careful 'at sea' operations to obtain the annelids in good condition and appropriate conditions in the aquaria. Is 10 degrees C truly indicative of the habitat at 300 m for the Trondheim Fjord? Certainly, this is appropriate for surface water if seasonality is not taken into account, but what about at depth? In addition, there is no accounting for the pressure that the annelids will experience at 300 m. As such, the laboratory conditions are very much experimental conditions. This is not, of itself, a criticism, but this should be reflected in the text with some discussion of relevance to the natural environment in which the annelids live.
- It would have been useful to have had the risk before and after mitigation measures. For example, where the risk is low to moderate, do the mitigation measures actually take the risk from moderate to low? What are the consequences of the mitigation measures on the high risk WP4?
- The conceptual risk (importance of bioluminescence for communication and the change in behaviour of captured specimens) goes to the core of the concern about this project, which could have been mitigated by some more compelling preliminary data supporting the basic hypothesis about plankton bioluminescence.

Selected mark : 5 - Very good

The proposal addresses the criterion very well. A small number of shortcomings are present.

Impact

Potential impact of the proposed research

- Potential for academic impact:

The extent to which the planned outputs of the project address important present and/or future scientific challenges. The extent to which the planned outputs are openly accessible to ensure reusability of the research outputs and enhance reproducibility.

- Potential for societal impact (if addressed by the applicant):

The extent to which the planned outputs of the project address UN Sustainable Development Goals or other important present and/or future societal challenges.

- The extent to which the potential impacts are clearly formulated and plausible.

Communication and exploitation

- The extent to which the appropriate open science practices are implemented as an integral part of the proposed project to ensure open sharing and wide distribution of research outputs.
- Quality and scope of communication and engagement activities with different target audiences, including relevant stakeholders/users.

Strengths

- + The demonstration of the potential reception of bioluminescence and the associated nervous circuit in annelids is of fairly narrow scope in the context of the proposal, but it is an important unexplored area and can stimulate in the future a novel study area, which is excellent.
- + This novel research line is poised to have strong, academic impact on the fields of neuroscience and, more generally, on the ecological aspects of deep-sea bioluminescence. The work can contribute to UN SDG 14a (life below water).
- + There is excellent consideration and commitment to data outputs and accessibility, which demonstrates an understanding and serious concern about data reusability.
- + There is a clear and convincing quality and scope of the communication and engagement activities, which is excellent. The deep sea catches the public imagination. When you connect this with colour and significant visual opportunities, more could have been made of this project contributing to ocean literacy.

Shortcomings

- The first measure for monitoring successful project impact, the completion of each WP, is inapposite. It is unclear what is meant by completion. There may be unexpected results which impact the direction of travel. Given this is a potentially high impact, novel programme, the expectation that the WPs will be completed is too simplistic.
- The potential scientific impact is overstated and naive with regards to the understanding of the function and relevance of bioluminescence in the broader marine domain. The annelids are unlikely to be representative of all planktonic animals and so statements about how the project will expand general understanding of the role of light in all marine organisms are not very convincing.
- Some indication of monitoring of impact and improving activities through feedback would have further strengthened communication and engagement.

Selected mark : 5 - Very good

The proposal addresses the criterion very well. A small number of shortcomings are present.

Implementation

The quality of the project manager and project group

- The extent to which the project manager has relevant expertise and experience, and demonstrated ability to perform high-quality research (as appropriate to the career stage).
- The degree of complementarity of the participants and the extent to which the project group has the necessary expertise needed to undertake the research effectively.

The quality of the project organisation and management

- Effectiveness of the project organisation, including the extent to which resources assigned to work packages are aligned with project objectives and deliverables.
- Appropriateness of the allocation of tasks, ensuring that all participants have a valid role and adequate resources in the project to fulfil that role.
- Appropriateness of the proposed management structures and governance.

Strengths

- + The project PI has a strong and relevant academic expertise in neuroscience but expertise in marine neuroscience, or marine biology with annelids is not clearly represented in their CV, which reduces proposal credibility in relation to expertise.
- + The consortium members have complementary expertise, and the project brings together scientists with solid track records and the necessary expertise for project implementation. All partners have a clear role and are appropriately and clearly assigned to WPs in the project description and the Gantt chart, which is very good.
- + The necessary research infrastructures to carry out the research exists and strongly supports project feasibility.

Shortcomings

- There will be a small number of active researchers on this project. Although they will be supported by several collaborators, there is potentially a lot of responsibility on the PI, both in terms of running the project and training the post-doctoral worker and PhD student. Although there will be weekly core team meetings, the direction from the collaborators is limited, especially Prof Dunn. Given the responsibilities that the PI has taken on, and their moderate experience in project management the involvement of a mentor or someone from whom they can seek guidance during the programme would have strengthened the proposal.
- A clearer presentation of the project management structure and governance would have given further credibility to the project implementation particularly since some core tasks depend on collaborators from other institutions.

Selected mark : 5 - Very good

The proposal addresses the criterion very well. A small number of shortcomings are present.